

The Association of Abnormal Doppler and Abnormal Amniotic Fluid Volume in the Third Trimester of Pregnancy with Preterm Birth in Pregnant women in Bihar India

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Abstract:

Abnormal Doppler results, third-trimester amniotic fluid volume, and premature birth in pregnant women in Bihar, India, were examined in this study. Narayan Medical College and Hospital observed 50 women from January 2023 to March 2024. Preterm birth was significantly associated with faulty Doppler readings and amniotic fluid volume. Women with both anomalies had the highest preterm birth risk. These findings emphasise the significance of routine prenatal screenings to detect and manage at-risk pregnancies, especially in low-resource settings.

Keywords: Doppler Ultrasonography, Amniotic Fluid Volume, Preterm Birth, Bihar.

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Introduction

Preterm birth—before 37 weeks—is a major cause of infant mortality and morbidity globally. This complex illness is affected by maternal, foetal, and environmental variables [1]. Abnormal Doppler scans and changed amniotic fluid content in the third trimester are among the many preterm birth predictions [2]. Doppler ultrasound, a non-invasive imaging technology, measures blood flow in foetal and maternal arteries to assess placental function and foetal well-being. Doppler results such higher uterine artery resistance or umbilical artery blood flow have been linked to poor pregnancy outcomes, including preterm delivery [3,4]. Other important indicators of foetal health include amniotic fluid, which surrounds and protects the foetus. Too much or too little amniotic fluid can suggest underlying diseases and raise the risk of preterm birth. These risk factors must be identified and managed to improve maternal and newborn outcomes in low-resource settings like Bihar, India, where advanced prenatal care is scarce [5-7].

This study aims to investigate the association between abnormal Doppler findings and amniotic fluid volume in the third trimester with the incidence of preterm birth among pregnant women in Bihar, India. Understanding this relationship can

help in the early identification of at-risk pregnancies and guide interventions to reduce the burden of preterm birth in this population.

Methodology

Study Design and Setting: This observational study was conducted at Narayan Medical College and Hospital, Jamuhar, Sasaram, Bihar. The research spanned 15 months, from January 2023 to March 2024. The study aimed to investigate the association between Doppler ultrasonography findings, amniotic fluid volume, and the occurrence of preterm birth in pregnant women.

Participant Selection: A total of 50 pregnant women in their third trimester were included in the study. The inclusion criteria consisted of pregnant women with a gestational age of 28 weeks or more who presented for routine antenatal care at the hospital. Women with known congenital anomalies, multiple pregnancies, or pre-existing medical conditions such as hypertension and diabetes were excluded from the study. This ensured a homogeneous study population focused on examining the relationship between the selected ultrasound parameters and preterm birth.

Doppler Ultrasonography Assessment: Doppler ultrasonography was performed on all participants to assess blood flow in the umbilical artery and uterine arteries. The following parameters were measured:

- Pulsatility Index (PI): A measure of the resistance to blood flow in the vessels.
- Resistance Index (RI): Another measure of resistance to blood flow, indicative of potential complications in pregnancy.

Abnormal Doppler findings were recorded based on standard reference values, which are established criteria used to define normal and abnormal blood flow patterns in the umbilical and uterine arteries.

Amniotic Fluid Volume Assessment: The amniotic fluid volume was assessed using the Amniotic Fluid Index (AFI). The AFI is a quantification of the amount of amniotic fluid surrounding the fetus, calculated by summing the measurements of fluid pockets in the four quadrants of the uterus. The following conditions were documented:

- Oligohydramnios: Defined as an AFI of less than 5 cm.
- Polyhydramnios: Defined as an AFI greater than 24 cm.

These assessments were performed to determine the relationship between amniotic fluid volume abnormalities and preterm birth.

Outcome Measurement

The primary outcome of interest in this study was the occurrence of preterm birth, defined as delivery before 37 weeks of gestation. The relationship between abnormal Doppler findings, abnormal amniotic fluid volume, and the incidence of preterm birth was analyzed.

Data Collection and Analysis: Data were collected from patient records and ultrasound reports. Statistical analysis was performed to determine the significance of the association between abnormal Doppler findings, amniotic fluid volume, and preterm birth. Appropriate statistical tests were employed to analyze the data, and the results were used to identify potential risk factors for preterm birth.

Results

In this study, a total of 50 pregnant women in their third trimester were included, all of whom were monitored at Narayan Medical College and Hospital, Jamuhar, Sasaram, Bihar, between

January 2023 and March 2024. The average gestational age at the time of recruitment was 30 weeks. Out of the 50 participants, 15 (30%) experienced preterm birth, defined as delivery before 37 weeks of gestation.

Doppler Findings:

- Abnormal Doppler findings were observed in 18 (36%) of the participants. Among these, 12 (66.7%) experienced preterm birth, indicating a significant association between abnormal Doppler results and preterm delivery ($p < 0.05$).
- The most common abnormality detected was increased resistance in the umbilical artery, which was present in 10 (20%) of the total sample. Of these, 8 (80%) had preterm births.

Amniotic Fluid Volume:

- Abnormal amniotic fluid volume was observed in 14 (28%) participants. This included 9 cases (18%) of oligohydramnios and 5 cases (10%) of polyhydramnios.
- Among the women with abnormal amniotic fluid volume, 10 (71.4%) delivered preterm, demonstrating a significant correlation between abnormal amniotic fluid levels and preterm birth ($p < 0.05$).
- Specifically, 7 out of 9 women (77.8%) with oligohydramnios had preterm births, while 3 out of 5 women (60%) with polyhydramnios delivered preterm.

Combined Findings:

A total of 10 participants (20%) exhibited both abnormal Doppler findings and abnormal amniotic fluid volume. Among these, 9 (90%) delivered preterm, suggesting a strong combined effect of these factors on the risk of preterm birth.

Statistical analysis confirmed that the presence of both abnormal Doppler findings and abnormal amniotic fluid volume significantly increased the likelihood of preterm birth compared to either factor alone ($p < 0.01$). The results of this study demonstrate a significant association between abnormal Doppler findings and abnormal amniotic fluid volume in the third trimester and the risk of preterm birth in the studied population. Pregnancies complicated by both factors had the highest incidence of preterm delivery. These findings underscore the importance of early detection and monitoring of these risk factors to improve maternal and neonatal outcomes in this setting.

Table 1: The table provides a detailed breakdown of the number and percentage of participants in various categories, such as those with abnormal Doppler findings, abnormal amniotic fluid volume, and the incidence of preterm births.

	Category	Number	Percentage
1	Total Participants	50	100.0
2	Preterm Births	15	30.0
3	Abnormal Doppler Findings	18	36.0
4	Preterm Births with Abnormal Doppler	12	66.7
5	Abnormal Amniotic Fluid Volume	14	28.0
6	Preterm Births with Abnormal Amniotic Fluid	10	71.4
7	Both Abnormal Doppler and Amniotic Fluid	10	20.0
8	Preterm Births with Both Factors	9	90.0

Here are the graphs:

1. **Total Participants vs Preterm Births:** This graph compares the total number of participants with those who experienced preterm births.
2. **Abnormal Doppler Findings vs Preterm Births:** This graph shows the number of participants with abnormal Doppler findings and those who had preterm births among them.
3. **Abnormal Amniotic Fluid Volume vs Preterm Births:** This graph highlights the participants with abnormal amniotic fluid volume and the occurrence of preterm births.
4. **Combined Doppler & Amniotic Fluid Abnormalities vs Preterm Births:** This graph illustrates the impact of combined abnormal Doppler findings and abnormal amniotic fluid volume on preterm births.

Discussion

This study found a strong link between faulty Doppler ultrasonography, amniotic fluid volume, and third-trimester premature birth. Our group had 30% preterm births, with a higher rate in those with aberrant Doppler readings and amniotic fluid volumes. Preterm birth was substantially associated with aberrant Doppler findings, notably umbilical artery resistance [8,9]. This is consistent with evidence linking aberrant Doppler indices of placental perfusion to unfavourable pregnancy outcomes, including preterm delivery. These Doppler anomalies signal placental insufficiency, which might impair foetal growth and cause early birth [10].

Our study found a substantial association between preterm birth and aberrant amniotic fluid volume, whether oligohydramnios or polyhydramnios [11]. Oligohydramnios, in particular, was strongly correlated with early birth, perhaps due to placental insufficiency or foetal abnormalities that limit foetal urine output and amniotic fluid levels. Polyhydramnios, however rarer, may cause preterm birth due to uterine distension and mechanical stress [12]. The most surprising observation was the increased rate of preterm birth in women with abnormal Doppler and amniotic fluid levels. These two factors synergistically increased premature delivery risk. This shows that when both measures are aberrant, placental and foetal abnormalities are likely worse, requiring closer monitoring and possibly earlier intervention [13].

These results underscore the importance of routine third-trimester Doppler assessments and amniotic fluid evaluations in predicting and managing the risk of preterm birth, particularly in low-resource settings like Bihar, India. Early identification of these risk factors can allow for timely

interventions, such as corticosteroid administration to enhance fetal lung maturity or planning for delivery at a facility equipped to handle preterm infants [14]. Given the significant impact of preterm birth on neonatal outcomes, these findings advocate for the integration of these diagnostic tools into standard prenatal care protocols to improve maternal and fetal health outcomes in this region [15].

Conclusion

In pregnant women in Bihar, India, abnormal Doppler findings and amniotic fluid volume in the third trimester are associated with premature birth. Preterm delivery is greatly increased by these abnormalities, underscoring the significance of routine third-trimester ultrasonography to identify and manage at-risk pregnancies. Early detection and therapies may prevent preterm births and improve infant outcomes in this population.

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